

Effects Of Rehabilitation Counselling and Rational Emotive Behaviour Therapy on the Reduction of Recidivism Among Prison Inmates in Correctional Centre of Ebonyi State

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Abstract

This study investigated the effects of rehabilitation counselling and rational emotive behaviour therapy on the reduction of recidivism among prison inmates in correctional centre of Ebonyi State. Three research questions and three null hypotheses guided the study. The specific design for this study is a non-equivalent pretest-posttest control group design, with the experimental group adopting rehabilitation counselling, rational emotive behaviour therapy and the combination of rehabilitation counselling and rational emotive behaviour therapy and the control group using the conventional counselling approach. The sample for this study was 40 prison inmates with recidivism in correctional service of Ebonyi based on the preliminary survey conducted by the researcher. The study adopted a pre-test, post-test, control group experimental design. Two instruments titled "Recidivism Identification Questionnaire (RIQ) and Recidivism Reduction Questionnaire (RRQ) were developed by the researchers for the study. The stability of RC and REBT were established using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation co-efficient and reliability estimate of 0.86 and 0.89 were reported. The internal consistency of the items was determined using Cronbach's Alpha method which yielded a reliability estimate of 0.89 and 0.86 respectively. Data obtained through the administration of the RIQ and RRQ were organized and analyzed using mean scores, standard deviation and analysis of covariance (ANCOVA), which revealed the following findings: there is a significant difference in the reduction of prison inmates recidivism mean scores of subjects treated with rehabilitation counselling and those in control group, there is a significant difference in the reduction of recidivism means scores of subjects treated with rational emotive therapy and those in control group and there is a significant

difference in the reduction of prison inmates recidivism mean scores of subjects treated with the combination of rehabilitation counselling and rational emotive therapy and those in control group. It was concluded that RC and REBT were effective in reducing recidivism.

Keywords: *Rehabilitation Counselling (RC), Rational Emotive Behaviour Therapy (REBT), Recidivism*

Introduction

Human society is complex. Sociologists and psychologists have identified the nature and scope of this complexity. In every human society, individuals may be good or bad, rational or irrational. Concerned about these social misfits, civilized society decided to introduce an institution where these misfits can be kept for the safety of other members of the society and possibly for rehabilitation. Consistent with the foregoing a prison is a place, space used to confine criminal or people convicted or awaiting trial. It includes the land, the house and every other structure located within the institution used for the purpose of detention (Alex, 2013). A prison is also known as a correctional facility in which inmates (or prisoners) are forcibly confined and denied a variety of freedom under the authority of the state (Appelbaum, Hickey & Packer, 2011). Prison inmate or detainee is a person who is deprived of liberty against his/her will (Guibaud, 2010). This could be by confinement, captivity or by forcible restraint.

The Nigeria Correctional Centre was established under the Nigerian Prisons Act Cap.29 Laws of the Federation of Nigeria, 2014. The National Assembly of the Federal Republic of Nigeria enacted a new Prisons and Correctional Centre Bill in 2016 with comprehensive provisions for the administration of prisons in Nigeria. One of the unique features of this new bill is that it has formally introduced the concept of 'corrections' into Prisons lexicon. The primary responsibility within the criminal justice system and that of the Nigerian Prisons Centre is to contribute to the public safety and security by ensuring safe custody and social rehabilitation of offenders for community reintegration (FGN, 2016).

Prison is an organization and administration in the form of social clinic in which psychologists, counsellors, medical doctors, social workers, researchers, spiritual workers, and others operate hand in hand with the correctional personnel to achieve the best results of transforming and rehabilitating the inmates away from being deviants to being disciplined, productive, useful and patriotic citizens (Nwolise, 2010). According to Onyechi and Okere (2016), prison is a correctional facility in which individuals are confined and denied a variety of freedom under the authority of the state as a form of punishment.

A prisoner is a person who is deprived of liberty against his or her will. This can be by confinement, captivity, or by forcible restraint. The term applies particularly to serving a prison sentence in a prison. This term does not apply to defendants who are pre-trial (Colvin & Mark, 2010). In this regard, there is need for professional counsellors and counselling association of Nigeria as a body in surmounting the obstacle faced by the prison inmates through various strategies in counselling such as, educational counselling, career counselling, rehabilitation, rational emotive therapy and reintegration for productive employment and self-reliant (Tenibiaje, 2013).

The Nigeria Correctional Centre functions are to take custody of any person pursuant to order of court; provide safe, secure and humane custody for prisoners; convey remand prisoners to and from courts in motorized formations; identify the causes of anti-social behaviours of convicted prisoners; set in motion mechanism for reforming and rehabilitating and re-integrating prisoners into the society; analyse crime and crime trends in order to evolve treatment methods compatible to the various regions and cultural structures therein; initiate behaviour modification in inmates through the provision of medical, psychological, uniformed chaplaincy and counselling services; provide opportunities for vocational skill acquisition for prison inmates and generating revenue in the process empower prisoners through the deployment of vast educational resources in the prison; and carry out other functions as may be prescribed by the National Assembly (Nigerian Prisons and Correctional Bills, 2016).

In Nigeria during the period of incarceration inmates are required to undergo suitable rehabilitation programme including vocational education and training. All these activities are aimed at equipping the inmates with necessary skills that would enable them to actively participate in positive socio-economic engagements upon release. Offenders, whether adult or juveniles, convicts or simply remand are usually offered some sort of vocational training during the period of incarceration. For most prison centre establishments, training seems to be elevated to a position of utmost prominence, so much so that an offender's post-release career seems to depend largely on the success of training received in prison. Prison vocational training should address the vital aspects of offender rehabilitation and reintegration, and current agitations centre on whether offender should 'do time' or 'use time' during training sessions. By and large, training should not simply be part of prison routine, but instead should have firm features of an intervention, and also represent a treatment regime (Greg, 2013). The assumption of rehabilitation is that people are not permanently criminal and that it is possible to restore a criminal recidivism.

Reintegration of former inmates back into society is not only necessary, but imperative for overall benefit. Failure of reintegration leads the ex-offender to re-offend (Raphael, 2011). This would then produce new victims of various crimes. Without a thriving reintegration programme through counselling techniques many prisoners in transition will continue to suffer with psychological issues and low employment rates, this too, leads to recidivism (Lynch & Sabook, 2016). The researchers such as (Ogundipe, 2016) experience in the Nigerian prison Centre for over ten years has indicated that out of four prisoners discharged, three eventually comes back to the prison more than four times within two years of their release as recorded by (NPC, 2018). These habitual prisoners are known as recidivists. Recidivism is described by Lynch and Sabook (2016) as a repeated undesirable behaviour which is demonstrated even after experiencing negative consequences for these behaviours. Recidivism is a tendency to lapse into a previous pattern of behaviour, especially a pattern of criminal habits.

Recidivism means the re-arrest, reconviction or re-incarceration of former inmates (Ifaturo, 2017). Edward (2016) further opined that recidivism is one of the most fundamental concepts in criminal justice. It refers to a person's relapse into criminal behaviour often after the person receives sanctions or undergoes intervention for a previous crime. Recidivism is measured by criminal acts that resulted in the re-arrest,

reconviction or return to prison with or without a new sentence during a three-year period following the prisoner's release. Recidivism cuts across all nations in the world with its negative consequences on individuals, and the social and economic spheres of life. Despite various intervention strategies, the rate of recidivism has been on the increase. This calls for concerns and a need to find a solution to this social malaise. In Nigeria the rate at which released inmates return back into the person (recidivist) few months upon release has attracted the attentions and interest of criminologist, sociologists, counsellors, psychologists and scholars from other disciplines. Recidivism is the reversion of criminal acts of an offender who has been subjected to punitive sanctions/acts. There is no consensus of opinion among social science scholars especially criminologists on the significant determinants of recidivism among prison inmates.

A recidivist or a person habitually addicted to crime is one who is a criminal by habit or by disposition formed by the repetition of crime (Edward, 2016). These are the persons who have embraced criminality as a mode of life and commit crime with boldness. Recidivism is now a common phenomenon among inmates in the Nigerian prisons. These include both male and female offenders/inmates in the Nigerian prison custody. Soyombo (2019) reported that the prevalence of criminal recidivism in Nigeria in 2013 was 37.3%. Wilson (2016) also reported that studies conducted in Nigeria have documented that 81% of male criminal inmate offenders and 45% of female criminal inmates' offenders were rearrested within 36 months of discharge/release from the prison custody. Abrifor (2010) estimated the prevalence of recidivism in Nigerian prisons at 52.4%. Since then, there has not been any indication that the trend has declined.

This trend in the high prevalence of recidivism shows that in Nigeria and in many other countries globally, prison consensus results have shown high rate of inmates' release and high rate of inmates' recidivism. As a result of this, crime by former inmates alone account for a substantial share of current and future crimes. From this background, peace, safety of lives and property are threatened thereby affecting the rate of investment in social and economic growth and developmental processes. Thus, it becomes imperative to restructure the irrational thinking of these prison inmates, looking at the causes and principles for the reduction of recidivism among inmates in Nigeria prisons and the accompanying challenges on both social and economic development in Nigeria.

Current statistics on recidivism in Ebonyi State Correctional Custodian Centre of Nigeria indicated high rate of recidivism among released prisoners. The researcher tracked 47,379 prisoners in two prisons (Abakaliki & Afikpo) for 2014 and 2015 respectively and those that returned back within three years were 9475, that is approximately 20 per cent. Within two years: 42.22 per cent were rearrested (almost exclusively for felonies or serious misdemeanours) 33.77 per cent were reconvicted and 24.01 per cent were resented to prison for new crimes. Ekpe and Mammah in Ugwuoke (2010) noted that government seems to have little or no provision for gainful employment opportunities or arrangement for proper rehabilitation of discharged prisoners in the society. The social stigma "ex-convict" attached to them seems to have contribution to their problem of resettlement in the society. There are countless alternatives to consider as

a means of ameliorating the problem of recidivism. It involves a complete overhaul of the societal values concerning justice, punishment, and second chances because research has shown that treatment effectiveness of behavioural problems among prison inmates should include rehabilitation counselling therapy and rational emotive therapy (Fhooblall, Chittoo & Bholoa, 2019). In this study, the researcher examined the effect of rehabilitation counselling therapy and rational emotive in reduction of recidivism among prison inmates.

In Bolton (2011), defined rehabilitation counselling as consideration of all efforts to help the individual adjust psychologically and behaviourally to a variety of life processes such as work, interpersonal relations and other processes by which a person is restored in a state of optimal effectiveness and given an opportunity to enjoy a meaningful life. Similarly, the National Rehabilitation Counselling Association (NRCA) defined rehabilitation counselling as a systematic process which assists persons with physical, development, cognitive and emotional disabilities to achieve their personal, career and independent living through the application of the counselling process (Chan, Berven & Thomas, 2014). Rehabilitation counselling consists of efforts to help inmates adjust psychologically, behaviourally, vocationally to a variety of life processes at school, workplace and the community at large. It is a total process by which an inmate is restored to a state of optimal effectiveness and given an opportunity to enjoy a meaningful life after jail term. Rehabilitation counselling is thus both preventive and restorative directed towards self-improvement, personal competence and improving of functions. Counsellors who work in correctional institutions could help turn the custodial system into helping system. Many offenders land into prison because they are not capable of utilizing and tapping their inherent potentials and resources. The purpose of counselling for prison inmates is to inculcate in them the will to live a good and useful life on discharge (Nanram&Asabe, 2019).

The next therapy to be employed to reduce recidivism is Rational Emotive behavioural therapy (REBT). It is used to reduce recidivism among prison inmates in Nigeria (Ekechukwu, 2014). REBT, previously called rational therapy and rational emotive therapy, is an active-directive, philosophically and empirically based psychotherapy. The aim of REBT is to resolve emotional and behavioural problems and disturbances and to help people to lead happier and more fulfilling lives (Paul & Iwuama, 2011). REBT proponent such as Albert Ellis holds that humans are prone to adopting irrational beliefs and behaviours which stand in the way of their achieving their goals and purposes. Most importantly, REBT maintains that, individuals are capable of changing their beliefs and philosophies profoundly, and thereby able to change radically their state of psychological health. In addition, psychological health, thought of inadequacy, worthlessness, hopelessness, self-blame and pessimism are symptoms of recidivism that interfere with normal functioning, so that the individuals have trouble concentrating and making decisions which may lead to emotional, behavioural and cognitive consequences. Although, we may not always be aware of our thoughts, they nevertheless can have a long effect on how we feel and behave in response to a particular situation or event (Albert Ellis cited in Ekechukwu, 2017).

Some studies have been carried out in this area. Chukwu (2012) investigated the effects of desensitization therapies on the reduction of anxiety among inmates in Nigeria prisons. Tenibiaje (2013) studied the educational attainment and peer group influence as predictors of recidivism in Nigeria. Abrifor, Atere and Moughalu (2013), examined gender differences, trend and patterns of recidivism among inmates in selected Nigeria prisons. Thus, the researchers explored the effects of rehabilitation counselling therapy and rational emotive therapy in reduction of recidivism among prison inmates in Ebonyi State correctional facilities. This therefore has necessitated this study.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

What is the difference in the pre-test-post-test means scores of prison inmate exposed to rehabilitation counselling in the reduction of recidivism and the control?

- 1) What is the difference in the pre-test post-test mean scores of prison inmate exposed to rational emotive therapy in the reduction of recidivism and the control?
- 2) What is the difference in the pre-test post-test mean scores of prison inmate exposed to rehabilitation counselling and rational emotive therapy in the reduction recidivism and the control?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- Ho₁:** There is no significant difference in pre-test-post-test mean scores of prison inmates exposed to rehabilitation counselling in the reduction of recidivism and the control.
- Ho₂:** There is no significant difference in pre-test post-test mean scores of prison inmates exposed to rational emotive therapy in the reduction of recidivism and the control.
- Ho₃:** There is no significant difference pre-test post-test mean scores of prison inmates exposed to rehabilitation counselling and rational emotive therapy in the reduction of recidivism and the control.

Methods

The sample for this study was 40 prison inmates with recidivism in correctional service of Ebonyi based on the preliminary survey conducted by the researchers. The study adopted a pre-test, post-test, control group experimental design. The specific design for this study is a non-equivalent pretest-posttest control group design, with the experimental group adopting rehabilitation counselling, rational emotive behaviour therapy and the combination of rehabilitation counselling and rational emotive behaviour therapy and the control group using the conventional counselling approach. Two instruments titled “Recidivism Identification Questionnaire (RIQ) and Recidivism Reduction Questionnaire (RRQ) were developed by the researchers or the study. The stability of RC and REBT using Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation coefficient and reliability estimate of 0.86 and 0.89 respectively. The internal consistency of the items was

determined using Cronbach's Alpha method which yielded a reliability estimate of 0.89 and 0.86 respectively. Data obtained through the administration of the instruments were analyzed using mean scores, standard deviation and analysis of covariance (ANCOVA).

Results

Research Question 1

What is the difference in the pre-test-post-test means scores of prison inmate exposed to rehabilitation counselling in the reduction of recidivism and the control?

Table 1.1: Pretest-Posttest Mean Scores in the Reduction of Recidivism among the Subjects Treated with Rehabilitation Counselling and the Control Group

Treatment Group		Pre-Test	Post Test	Mean gain/Loss
Experimental group	Mean	50.67	26.54	-24.13
	N	20	20	
	SD	5.72	5.93	
Control group	Mean	51.21	22.67	-28.54
	N	20	20	
	SD	7.25	8.14	

Data in Table 1.1 showed the mean scores in the difference in the reduction of recidivism among the subjects treated with rehabilitation counselling and the control group. From the data, one can see that the subjects in the experimental group had a pretest mean score of 50.67 and standard deviation of 5.72 in their recidivism self-scoring reduction scale; while their post-test means recidivism reduction score was 26.54 with a standard deviation of 5.93; giving a mean pre-test/post-test loss score of -24.13. The subjects not treated with rehabilitation counselling (control group) had a pretest mean recidivism reduction score of 51.21 with a standard deviation of 7.25 while their post-test mean score was 22.67 with a standard deviation of 8.14. This gives a pretest-test/posttest mean loss score of -28.54. The experimental group that was exposed to rehabilitation counselling had a lower mean prison inmate recidivism reduction score than the subjects in the control group.

A corresponding hypothesis formulated to further address the research question is:

Hypothesis One

There is no significant difference in pre-test-post-test mean scores of prison inmates exposed to rehabilitation counselling in the reduction of recidivism and the control.

Table 1.2: Summary of the 2-Way Analysis of Covariance of Reduction of Recidivism among the Subjects Treated with Rehabilitation Counselling and the Control Group

Source	Type III sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F	Sig
Corrected model	358.827 ^a	4	358.827 ^a	1.790	.000
Intercept	283.277	1	283.277	5.653	.000
Pre-SDT	10.598	1	10.598	.211	.648
Treatment	183.760	1	183.760	3.667	.000
Gender	68.160	1	68.160	1.360	.250
Treatment*Gender	93.913	1	93.913	1.874	.178
Error	2154.652	35	50.108		
Total	31571.000	40			
Corrected Total	2513.479	39			

a. R Square = .143 (Adjusted R Square = .063).

The data in the Table 1.2 above showed that rehabilitation counselling as a factor in the study has a significant effect on prison inmates recidivism reduction of the subjects. The calculated f-value of 3.667 in respect of difference in the reduction of recidivism mean scores of subjects treated with rehabilitation counselling and those in control group is higher than f-value/critical value of 1.96 (0.05). Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant difference in pre-test-post-test mean scores of prison inmates exposed to rehabilitation counselling in the reduction of recidivism and the control is rejected. Consequently, there is a significant difference in the reduction of prison inmates recidivism mean scores of subjects treated with rehabilitation counselling and those in control group.

Research Question 2

What is the difference in the pre-test post-test mean scores of prison inmate exposed to rational emotive therapy in the reduction of recidivism and the control?

Table 2.1: Pretest-Posttest Mean Scores in the Reduction of Recidivism among the Subjects Treated with Rational Emotive Therapy and the Control Group

Treatment Group		Pre-Test	Post Test	Mean/gain/Loss
Experimental group	Mean	51.63	26.92	-24.71
		20	20	
	N	5.87	5.01	
	SD			
Control group	Mean	51.21	22.67	-28.54
	N	20	20	
	SD	6.78	8.14	

Data in Table 2.1 showed the mean scores in the difference in the reduction of recidivism among the subjects treated with rational emotive therapy and the control group. From the data, one can see that the subjects in the experimental group had a pretest mean score of 51.63 and standard deviation of 5.87 in their prison inmates recidivism self-scoring reduction scale; while their post-test means recidivism reduction score was 26.92 with a standard deviation of 5.01. This gives a mean pre-test/post-test loss score of -24.71. The inmates not treated with rational emotive therapy (control group) had a pretest mean recidivism reduction score of 51.21 with a standard deviation of 6.78 while their post-test mean score was 22.67 with a standard deviation of 8.14. This gives a pre-test/posttest mean loss score of -28.54. The experimental group that was exposed to rational emotive therapy had a lower mean recidivism reduction point score than the subject in the control group.

A corresponding hypothesis formulated to further address the research question is:

Hypothesis Two

There is no significant difference in pre-test post-test mean scores of prison inmates exposed to rational emotive therapy in the reduction of recidivism and the control.

Table 2.2: Summary of the 2-Way Analysis of Covariance of Recidivism among the Subjects Treated with Rational Emotive Therapy and the Control Group

Source	Type III sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F	Sig
Corrected model	237.666 ^a	4	237.666 ^a	1.227	.000
Intercept	598.870	1	598.870	12.367	.000
Pre-SQS	18.082	1	18.082	.373	.544
Treatment	220.787	1	220.787	4.559	.000
Gender	3.493	1	3.493	.072	.790
Treatment*Gender	2.214	1	2.214	.046	.832
Error	2082.251	35	48.424		
Total	31822.000	40			
Corrected Total	2319.917	39			

a. R Square = .102 (Adjusted R Square = .019).

The data in the Table 2.2 above showed that rational emotive therapy has a significant effect on prison inmates recidivism reduction of the subjects. The calculated f-value of 4.559 in respect of difference in the reduction of recidivism mean scores of subjects treated with rational emotive therapy and those in control group is higher than f-value/critical value of 1.96 (0.05). Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant difference in pre-test post-test mean scores of prison inmates exposed to rational emotive therapy in the reduction of recidivism and the control is rejected. Consequently, there is a significant difference in

the reduction of recidivism mean scores of subjects treated with rational emotive therapy and those in control group.

Research Question 3

What is the difference in the pre-test post-test mean scores of prison inmate exposed to rehabilitation counselling and rational emotive therapy in the reduction recidivism and the control?

Table 3.1: Pretest-Posttest Mean Scores in the Reduction of Recidivism among the Subjects Treated with Combination of Rehabilitation Counselling and Rational Emotive Therapy and the Control Group

Treatment Group		Pre-Test	Post Test	Mean gain/Loss
Experimental group	Mean	50.63	25.00	-25.63
	N	20	20	
	SD	5.64	6.78	
Control group	Mean	51.75	22.67	- 29.08
	N	20	20	
	SD	6.92	8.14	

Data in Table 3.1 showed the mean scores in the difference in the reduction of recidivism among the subjects treated with combination of rehabilitation counselling and rational emotive therapy and the control group. From the data, one can see that the subjects in the experimental group had a pretest mean score of 50.63 and standard deviation of 5.64 in their prison inmates self-scoring reduction scale; while their post-test means recidivism reduction score was 25.00 with a standard deviation of 6.78. This gives a mean pre-test/post-test loss score of -25.63. The subjects not treated with the combination of rehabilitation counselling and rational emotive therapy (control group) had a pretest mean recidivism reduction score of 51.75 with a standard deviation of 6.92 while their post-test mean score was 22.67 with a standard deviation of 8.14. This gives a pre-test/posttest mean loss score of -29.08. The experimental group that was exposed to the combination of rehabilitation counselling and rational emotive therapy had a lower mean recidivism reduction point score than the subjects in the control group.

A corresponding hypothesis formulated to further address the research question is:

Hypothesis Three

There is no significant difference pre-test post-test mean scores of prison inmates exposed to rehabilitation counselling and rational emotive therapy in the reduction of recidivism and the control.

Table 3.2: Summary of the 2-Way Analysis of Covariance of the Reduction of Recidivism among the Subjects Treated with Combination of Rehabilitation Counselling and Rational Emotive Therapy and the Control Group

Source	Type III sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F	Sig
Corrected model	186.123 ^a	4	46.531 ^a	.813	.000
Intercept	591.834	1	591.834	10.343	.000
Pre-SDT &SQS	22.123	1	22.123	.387	.537
Treatment	58.063	1	58.063	4.715	.000
Gender	70.972	1	70.972	1.240	.272
Treatment*Gender	28.677	1	28.677	.501	.483
Error	2460.544	35	57.222		
Total	29912.000	40			
Corrected Total	2646.917	39			

a. R Square = .070 (Adjusted R Square = .016).

The data in the Table 3.2 above showed that the combination of rehabilitation counselling and rational emotive therapy as a factor in the study has a significant effect on recidivism reduction of the subjects. The calculated f-value of 4.715 in respect of difference in the reduction of recidivism mean scores of subjects treated with the combination of rehabilitation counselling and rational emotive therapy and those in control group is higher than f-value/critical value of 1.96 (0.05). Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant difference pre-test post-test mean scores of prison inmates exposed to rehabilitation counselling and rational emotive therapy in the reduction of recidivism and the control is rejected. Consequently, there is a significant difference in the reduction of prison inmates recidivism mean scores of subjects treated with the combination of rehabilitation counselling and rational emotive therapy and those in control group.

Discussion

The study investigated the effects of rehabilitation counselling and rational emotive behaviour therapy on the reduction of recidivism among prison inmates in correctional centres of Ebonyi State. The researchers found that there is a significant difference in the reduction of prison inmates recidivism mean scores of subjects treated with rehabilitation counselling and those in control group. The study was in line with previous intervention by Chan, Berven and Thomas (2014) which revealed that rehabilitation counselling therapy aid in reduction of recidivism among prison inmates. The internal and external locus of the experimental group (RCT) and the control group had a significant effect on the reduction of recidivism among prison inmates.

The finding is consistent with the assertion of Ekechukwu (2014) which indicated that REBT was very effective counselling technique in curbing the psychological effects of imprisonment. The study also found that there is a significant difference in the reduction of recidivism means scores of subjects treated with rational emotive therapy and those in control group. Furthermore, there is a significant difference in

the reduction of prison inmates recidivism mean scores of subjects treated with the combination of rehabilitation counselling and rational emotive therapy and those in control group. The study collaborated with Fhooblall, Chittoo and Bholoa (2019) the study revealed that there was a significant effect of the counselling therapy and rational emotive therapy on the self-esteem of inmates. In spite of the limitation noted, this study provided a new approach to deliver RC and REBT to offenders. Using RC and REBT, the rate of re-offenders reduced considerably. We can conclude that this study has suggested an innovative RC and REBT approach in reducing recidivism among inmates in correctional centres. Specifically, REBT therapy is an effective psychotherapy that reduced recidivism among inmates in Ebonyi State correctional centres in Nigeria. As this has provided a new REBT approach, future studies can explore the efficacy of this on larger

The smallness of the sample size is a major limitation which affects the extent to which the outcome of this study would be applied by RC and REBT counsellors and researchers. Besides, this study could not adjust for the effects of gender, age, education, prison sentence, ethnicity, religion and other prisoner characteristics on the treatment modality adopted.

Conclusion

Evidently, recidivism behaviour in Nigeria is a major problem. This study examined the effectiveness of rehabilitation counselling and rational emotive behaviour therapy on recidivism among prison inmates. Using RC and REBT, the rate of re-offenders reduced considerably. We can conclude that this study has suggested an innovative RC and REBT approach in reducing recidivism among inmates in correctional centres. Specifically, REBT therapy is an effective psychotherapy that reduced recidivism among inmates in Ebonyi State correctional centres in Nigeria.

Recommendation

Based on the observations from the study, it is recommended that the government should intensify efforts towards recruiting and deploying counsellors to the Nigerian Prisons Service to help curb the increasing incidence of recidivism behaviors among prison inmates in Nigeria. In addition, providing funds for research interventions targeting the prison populations would be a positive step on part of the Nigerian Government. Lastly, licensure of the counselling profession for counsellors in Nigeria, may spur them into action research for offenders and also devotedly extending their research activities, guidance and counselling practical works and behavioural change counselling services to all the prisons population in the country.

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